

Università
degli Studi di
Messina

HYCELTEC 2024

Book of abstracts

**IX Symposium on Hydrogen, Fuel Cells
and Advanced Batteries**
Milazzo (Italy) • June 30 - July 03, 2024

CURATORI/ EDITORS:

**Baglio Vincenzo; Specchia Stefania; Lufrano Francesco;
Lo Faro Massimiliano; Di Blasi Orazio; Squadrito Gaetano**

Editore/Publisher
Comitato Convegni EMHYTEC

Editore/Publisher
Comitato Convegni EMHYTEC

© **HYCELTEC 2024**

The authors of the papers are free to reuse the abstracts and the data submitted to HYCELTEC 2024 just referring to previous communication at the conference

The volume contains the collection of communications presented at the ninth edition of the Hyceltec conference held in Milazzo from 30 June to 3 July 2024. The conference is co-chaired by Vincenzo Baglio (CNR-ITAE) and Stefania Specchia (Turin Polytechnic University).

ISBN 978-88-942723-4-5

Data Pubblicazione
30/06/2024

Luogo di pubblicazione
Spadafora (ME), Italy

From Physical Properties to Performance: Understanding All-Vanadium Redox Flow Battery Electrolytes

Á. Ibáñez¹, J. Barroso², M. Montiel^{1,3}, F. Barreras¹

¹ Instituto de Carboquímica (ICB-CSIC), C/Miguel Luesma Castán, 4, 50018, Zaragoza, Spain

² Instituto Universitario de Investigación en Ingeniería de Aragón (I3A), Departamento de Ciencia y Tecnologías de Materiales y Fluidos, Universidad de Zaragoza, C/María de Luna 3, 50018, Zaragoza, Spain

³ Fundación Agencia Aragonesa para la Investigación y el Desarrollo (ARAID), Av. de Ranillas 1-D, 50018, Zaragoza, Spain

e-mail presenting author: a.ibanez@csic.es

Unlike other secondary batteries, in redox flow batteries the energy is stored in the electrolytes instead of the electrodes. In the specific case of all-vanadium redox flow batteries (VRFB), the electrolytes are solutions of vanadium salts ($V^{2+}/V^{3+} // VO_2^+/VO^{2+}$) in acidic medium [1]. Some of the advantages of VRFB are the absence of cross-contamination, since there are no different elements apart from vanadium in the active species; an independent capacity-to-power sizing and design; a long lifetime cycling, and the possibility to “restore” the capacity of the device by mixing and balancing the electrolytes, among others [2].

The electrolytes volume and concentrations define the battery capacity, and are key factors in the electrochemistry of the device. However, very few is written to date about the physical properties of the vanadium solutions and their impact on the battery performance, in comparison with other components such as the membranes or the porous electrodes [3]. This work focuses on the density, ρ , the dynamic viscosity, μ , and the surface tension, σ , of the VRFB electrolytes. Starting with commercial electrolyte, volumes of V(II), V(III), V(IV) and V(V) solution were produced using a lab-size redox flow battery. Then, various state-of-charge (SOC) samples for each of the two electrolytes were elaborated by mixing the original solutions in different proportion.

The density for both fluids, positive and negative electrolytes, was measured in a temperature (t) interval from 10 to 40 °C for the whole state of charge range using a digital vibrating densimeter. Viscosity measurements were performed in a Brookfield-type viscometer using an *ad hoc* designed spindle in order to avoid its corrosion. An in-house laboratory facility was designed and built to estimate the electrolytes surface tension by measuring the ascension height and the contact angle of the fluid in a capillary tube at different temperature and SOC conditions.

Mathematical correlations and uncertainties of experimental data are provided since they help to evaluate ρ , μ and σ in both positive and negative electrolytes as a function of the VRFB operation parameters (mainly SOC and temperature). A discussion about the influence of these properties on both the internal physics, the performance and the battery efficiency is also presented.

Figure 1: Left: Electrolyte droplet samples at different SOC. Right: Temperature-SOC density surface measured for the negative electrolyte.

References

- [1] M. Skyllas-Kazacos, M. Rychcik, R.G. Robins et al. J. Electrochem. Soc. (1986), 1057-1058.
- [2] H. Zhang, X. Li, J. Zhang, Redox Flow Batteries: Fundamentals and Applications (2017) 80-81.
- [3] M. Skyllas-Kazacos, L. Cao, M. Kazacos et al. ChemSusChem. 9 (2016), 1521-1543.